

EDUCATION OF TOLERANCE AT ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS IN THE CONTEXT OF TECHNOLOGY OF CULTURE DIALOGUES

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Annotation. *This article examines the phenomenon of tolerance education in foreign language lessons and shows that the most productive for this purpose of education is the use of the concept of the dialogue of cultures in the educational process of learning.*

Keywords: *tolerance formation, english language teaching, , crosscultural communication , person of culture ,education, dialogue*

Tolerance is one of the most important personality traits, extremely necessary for the development (and simply maintaining the viability) of all mankind. Tolerance is the very characteristic that ensures the success of both the individual and society and the state as a whole. And although the education of tolerance is the problem of the 21st century, the origins of tolerant and respectful attitude towards other cultures, religions, views lie in the very foundations of cultures and civilizations. The most important factor influencing the education of tolerance,

is the level of culture of the individual. The fall of the general cultural(basic) level of personality development inevitably exacerbates intercultural and interethnic contradictions. Therefore, although it is possible to form a tolerant consciousness in various ways, the most effective way, as pedagogical practice shows, is through familiarization with the cultural values of one's people, and through them - with the world. This is how the cultural experience of the individual is formed.

A cultural personality cannot be non-tolerant. Culture is the universal language of international communication. Therefore, it can serve as a universal means of forming a tolerant consciousness. An uncultured person carries a vacuum in his soul, a void that can be filled with anything, including bad habits,intolerance and etc. A cultured person is constantly busy, his soul performs incessant complex inner work, improving in this way. This work continues throughout life, for a person grows spiritually throughout his life. For the formation of cultural experience, it is also very important that it is laid down already from preschool age and develops over the years. This is served in modern conditions by the pedagogy of art, which through art forms and develops the cultural consciousness of students.

Currently, in the pedagogical process, the foreign language teachers faces a difficult task, which is not only to familiarize students with the diversity of cultures, but also to educate respect and tolerance towards other cultures. In addition, the teacher should be able to explain the term "tolerance". We are talking not only about the formulations associated with this term, but also about familiarity with all the nuances of tolerance. For the successful assimilation of the term "tolerance", it is necessary to understand what a tolerant person is, and for this purpose the teacher needs to tell about the qualities that are characteristics of such a person.

Communication in English is an intercultural interaction. It is very important to explain to the student that a foreign culture is no worse and no better than ours - it is just different, and these differences must be tolerated and understood. In our opinion, the use of the technology of dialogue of cultures is one of the most important means of educating tolerance in English language lessons. The dialogue of cultures is an exchange of opinions and experience,

comprehension of the values and traditions of other people. Teaching foreign language communication in the context of a dialogue of cultures involves an interconnected solution of the following communicative, educational, general educational and developmental tasks, namely:

1. Cognitive (culturological) aspect:

-activation of knowledge about the culture of English-speaking countries that is available in the experience of students;

-acquaintance with the culture of the country of the language being studied by comparing previously existing knowledge and concepts with newly acquired ones, with knowledge about one's country, one's area, about oneself;

development of students' abilities to represent their country and culture in the conditions of foreign language and intercultural communication.

2. Educational aspect:

the formation and development of the communicative culture of students, the development of a culture of oral presentations and writing in English;

development of the ability to translate and use a dictionary.

3. Developmental aspect:

-development of students' abilities to use English as a communication tool in the dialogue of cultures and civilizations of the modern world;

-development of intellectual skills and creative abilities of students in the collection, processing and interpretation of various types of cultural information;

-development of linguistic and regional studies and speech observation, creative imagination, associative and logical thinking in the conditions of foreign language educational communication;

-development of communication skills, independence, ability to cooperate.

4. Educational aspect:

-the formation of students' ideas about the dialogue of cultures as a consciously chosen philosophy of life, requiring from its participants respect for other cultures, linguistic, ethnic and racial tolerance, readiness to study the cultural heritage of the world, to spiritual enrichment with the achievements of other cultures, a deeper awareness of their native culture through the context of the culture of English-speaking countries; fostering a sense of patriotism, a sense of pride in one's culture, one's country; education of the need and ability for cooperation and mutual assistance.

Teaching a foreign language in the context of a dialogue of cultures contributes to the education of a person of culture who is committed to universal values, who has absorbed the richness of the cultural heritage of the past of his people and the peoples of other countries, who strives for mutual understanding with them, who is able and ready to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication, including by means of English language. The implementation of training and education in the context of culture contributes to a better assimilation of educational material, an increase in communicative and cognitive motivation, provides the possibility of simultaneously accessing language and culture, has a positive effect on the emotional state of students, contributes to the formation of students' tolerance for carriers of any cultural, religious, ethnic traditions, education personalities of the 21st century.

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